

1 **Ezh1 is a component of the trophectoderm differentiation program in human embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Ezh1
9 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Shen, X., Liu, Y., Hsu, Y.J., Fujiwara, Y., Kim, J., Mao, X., Yuan, G.C. and Orkin, S.H., 2008. EZH1
12 mediates methylation on histone H3 lysine 27 and complements EZH2 in maintaining stem cell identity
13 and executing pluripotency. Molecular cell, 32(4), pp.491-502.
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